

**Some Problems or Paradoxes in Letters relating to Columbus' Four Voyages to the
New World
by Brian Paul Kaess**

In this paper, I will try to point out some inconsistencies or problems related to Columbus' research as narrated by himself and his 'followers' in the Letters related to his first four voyages. In addition, I will summarize and make a sort of shorthand of the voyages themselves. Moreover, I will try to touch upon the Columbus-Vespucci Controversy, as I envision it, and add my own remarks as I deem necessary.

The outlines of the 1st voyage are clear enough. They started their epic sail on August 3, 1492, the fleet of the *Niña*, the *Pinta*, and the *Santa Maria*, leaving Palos de la Frontera. It is a myth that the Queen had to pawn her jewels to fund the voyage. They made several sightings of birds and vegetation in September and October, and finally sighted land on *San Salvador* (Watlings Island, Samana Cay, or Turks & Caicos, etc.) on October 12, 1492. It was not long before they made landfall. They eventually returned to Lisbon, Portugal on March 4, 1493, and reached Spain shortly thereafter.

In Christopher Columbus' 1st Letter¹, on page 15, he writes at the top: "They assure me that there is another island larger than Española, in which the inhabitants have no hair. It is extremely rich in gold; and I bring with me Indians taken from these different islands who will testify to all these things." But here Columbus mentions this as if he was almost unaware of the island of *Juana* (Cuba) which he had just come from, and which he certainly should have been aware of and perhaps interposed with his own knowledge during these conversations. For to the 1st island he gave the name *San Salvador*, and he goes on to say, "To the second island I gave the name of *Santa Maria de la Concepción*; the third I called *Fernandina*; the fourth, *Isabella*; the fifth, *Juana*; and so to each one I gave a new name." *Juana* is understood by most to be identical to the isle of Cuba.

So the question almost begs itself, if Columbus had already been aware of *Juana* (i.e., Cuba), why would he seem almost surprised when the natives mention this on *Española* or *Hispañiola*. We leave the question here to be treated by those who are more perspicacious than ourselves.

And here is another question that I may bring to your attention. On page 18, Columbus mentions: "In all the Indies I have always found the weather like that in the month of May. I reached them in thirty-three days and returned in twenty-eighty with the exception that these storms detained me fourteen days knocking about in this sea. All seamen say that they have never seen such a severe winter nor so many vessels lost." Now if this is indeed Columbus' 1st voyage to the Indies, and his is also the 1st royally-sponsored fleet to the Indies, by the Spanish Crown, what fleet are these vessels belonging too, which he refers to as lost or as never having seen 'so many vessels lost.' All he had in his own fleet were three vessels if I recall the lessons of my school teachers correctly!

¹ See *Select letters of Christopher Columbus : with other original documents, relating to his four voyages to the New World* , published in 1870 (London) by the Hakluyt Society.

Let us investigate further. In 1628, the Spanish treasure fleet, laden with booty, was caught off guard by the Dutch, led by Piet Heyn. The fleet, poorly managed, suffered catastrophic losses in either captured or destroyed vessels. But this occurred *in* the 17th century, long before Columbus' bones had found many a resting place!

In fact, many fleets were destroyed by storm or battle during the 16th-18th centuries. Not just the English or Dutch or French were tempted by these fleets, but privateers, buccaneers, and pirates as well². These fleets must have had few rivals, in terms of numbers, when they went down or destroyed. Was Columbus' sailors, living in 1492, referring to the natives themselves, in their flotillas of canoes? For surely, one is hard-pressed to understand why this 1st voyage in question is the one that had sailors bear witness to 'many vessels lost' when the number of vessels in any fleet they may have been aware of, in this time or place, appears limited to three.

Certainly, if a fleet, in the 1490s, rivaling one laden with loot from the Peruvian silver mines or Mexican gold stores, went down in the high seas close to the Indies, there would be more than just gibberish or scuttlebutt among sailors as a result, but talk among nobles back in Iberia regarding such a tragedy. And such talk would breed more than just a scant documentation for those times.

While we remain perplexed by this conundrum, let us move on to the 2nd voyage, which was documented by Columbus' physician in an epistle as stated by Andres Bernaldez³. This particular account was easily the most detailed regarding any letters pertaining to Columbus' voyages. The physician, Doctor Chanca, was appointed by dispatch, not only as a physician but also as a scrivener (or letter-writer) to the Indies and assigned a salary and rations as such. A slight problem almost immediately arises when he forgets to mark the year of the voyage in his notation, which would be September 25, 1493, if annotated correctly! A different source has the day of embarkation as Septmeber 24, 1493, from Cádiz⁴. This fleet was much larger than the previous one--with 17 ships and over 1,000 men. And the rest of his story is abundant in detail to be sure.

In Gomera (in the Canary Islands) they laid in meat, wood, and as much wáter as they could store. They were becalmed for a few days before leaving for the isle of Ferro in the southernmost and western Canaries, leaving there on October 13, 1493, to explore more 'unknown' lands. They sighted land within 20 days. On November 3, 1493, All Saints' Day- they sighted land. The pilot of the ship *Capitana* shouted out, 'the reward, I see the land!⁵' They had supposed they had made 800 leagues from Ferro and 1,100 leagues from Cádiz. They certainly had reason to be weary of bad living!

² See 'Spanish Treasure Fleets' in the *World History Encyclopedia* at worldhistory.org

³ See *Historia de la Reyes Católicos* by Andre Bernaldez.

⁴ ThoughtCo.com "The Second Voyage of Christopher Columbus"

⁵ See *Select letters of Christopher Columbus : with other original documents, relating to his four voyages to the New World*, p. 21.

They sighted the high mountains of the isle of *Dominica*, and six in total that day. This may not have seemed surprising to some that Columbus had among his crew pilots who could navigate by the stars to and from Spain! The mountains seemed green even up to the water. They put into harbor at *Marigalante*. Once again, Columbus landed with the royal banner and took possession on behalf of the Spanish Crown. They witnessed waterfalls, met the cannibals, and the physician noted how Columbus' 2nd Voyage arrived on a near-perfect tract, almost guiding them to *Española*. In some cases, the inhabitants fled as soon as they beheld the sails⁶.

They all appeared naked and wearing cloth appeared foreign to them. Curious and intelligent, many of the female captives were taken with their own consent⁷. Yet, there was evidence of butchery as the Spanish party came upon a vast host of human bones and skulls. Ironically, this group of Indians was the more civilized one!

When the Cannibals learned that the Spanish abhorred such people, they were delighted. Some women were captive, others native to this tribe. When attacking other tribes, some of the natives could sail for 150 leagues and their canoes could hold up to 60--80 men (including oars) as evinced by Columbus in his 1st letter. In their attacks upon the neighboring isles, they capture as many of the young and beautiful women as possible. One party of Spanish, that had been gone ten days, said that the trees had been so thick and close that they could not see the sky. Thus there was no way to navigate by the stars, and they had become lost.

Some of the islands had been depopulated by the Carribees. On the island of St. Martin, there was extensive cultivation, and it was populous. Some of the natives were stupefied with awe at the sight of the Spanish fleet. There were skirmishes between the Spanish and Carribees. Not all was tranquil in paradise!

Yet they noted they might bring away as much gold as they liked. Perhaps this insatiable lust drove them on. On *Santa Cruz* they found more than forty islets, the largest of which the Admiral called *St. Ursula*⁸. It was not long before they sighted *Española*. The one province they called Hayti, the other Xamana, and another Bohio, all being of great extent. It is believed to be 150 to 200 leagues long. They coasted for 100 leagues along this coast. There was a complaint that Spaniards had taken three or four women for themselves. They found a harbor of great security but far from any mine of gold!

They encountered deception by the natives but at least they would barter in gold, with parties sent to various islands. They believed the highnesses would be rich on account of the quantity of gold. It took awhile for the men to sleep onshore. They found trees bearing wool and cotton as well as wax from bees. Antonio de Torres, another of Columbus' captains, also wrote a letter on his behalf to the King and Queen.

⁶ *Ibid.* p. 26.

⁷ *Ibid.* p. 29.

⁸ *Ibid.* p. 38.

Of Columbus' third voyage, we will examine this through the lens of his own letter to the nurse of the *Prince John*, written in the year 1500⁹. Columbus notes that it is no novelty of the world to commit ill usage. In this regard, he feels reduced to the lowest ebb. Columbus' mantra seemed to be: "O man of little faith, arise, it is I, be not afraid."

The fleet of six ships left May 30, 1498, departing Spain. This must have been a humbler affair than the previous expedition. They reached *Trinidad* on July 31, 1498 and also marked the 1st time Columbus had reached the South American continent.

He states that he felt he would obtain honor because of the gold in *Española* and left orders to fish for pearls. He said he found half the colonists in a state of revolt¹⁰. He discovered *San Domingo* on August 13, 1498, and Alonzo de Hojeda, sent by the crown, reached *Española* on September 5, 1498, and attempted to quell some of the disorders, but Columbus said he began to trouble himself as well. In one case, a rebel, Adrian, was executed without Columbus having ordered it.

He wished to bring his Highnesses good news of the gold and had to wait six months to depart for Spain. If they would silence the rumors, it would be a real charity. He says mockingly, 'If I were to build schools or hospitals, they would call them caves for robbers!' He certainly wished to re-establish his reputation. He noted a woman could fetch as good a price as a farm. He furthermore states that a great number of men have been to the Indies who did not deserve baptism! He believes there is as much gold in the Indies as would be enough for every Spaniard to hoard one or two castellanos in a day.

He must no doubt be bitter about having been made a prisoner and Columbus mentions as much here. He seems, in this letter, to be more interested in detailing his complaints than the actual voyage. He remembers what the Lord said to him: "Take courage, be not dismayed nor fear, I will 'provide for all.'¹¹ ' He laments the just and honest inquisitor as nothing more than a despot. The tone of despair is such that you almost feel like you are reading Kierkegaard's *Fear and Trembling* (1843), instead of a letter written by a 'great explorer!'

By the time of this letter regarding his 4th Voyage (written in *Dominica*), Columbus still holds his post as Viceroy and Admiral of the Indies, once more addressing the King and Queen of Spain in lofty terms. He leaves on May 9, 1502, departing from Cádiz, Spain. Their aim is still to reach the West Indies. He returns after being marooned on Jamaica for a year, reaching Spain on November 7, 1504.

He dispatches a packet of letters on reaching the island of *Española*, mentioning the seas as some terrible tempest--only Job possessed more fear than himself! There is also complaint of profiting little from 20 years of toil and danger. But there was not any man to have such a litany of ills combined with such fame and glory.

⁹ *Ibid.* p. 152.

¹⁰ *Ibid.* p. 155.

¹¹ *Ibid.* p. 171.

His ship finally reaches the land of Cariay and takes in provisions for the next haul. Many places were mentioned that had gold and mines. We see the zest for riches always in the background for Columbus and his crew. But also inspired by the allure for the Indies, Columbus believed he could reach the Ganges in ten days' time. He also goes into a discourse on Ptolemy, and he is knowledgeable indeed, but he miscalculated the location of the Indies just a bit! He then returns to Puerto Gordo to recuperate and begins his journey anew. Columbus was no slacker. On Epiphany, they reach *Veragua* (i.e., the Caribbean coast of Panama). There was found a river and safe harbor. It then rains until February 14th. On Feb. 6, he took seventy men into the interior, presumably Panama here. It wasn't exactly 70 scribes in 70 rooms! Yet in Columbus, there was almost a divine hand at play.

We'll conclude our discussion of Columbus voyages by simply stating that he was a man of many firsts: 1) The first European to cross the Atlantic, 2) The first European to reach the Bahamas, 3) The first to use trade winds for navigation, 4) Finally, the first to establish Spanish colonies in the New World ¹².

While it may be believed by many that Columbus was first to cross the Atlantic, I point you to the lesser-known opinion that the Venetians were ignorant of the Icelandic *Sagas* until the 16th century. Perhaps we should not perpetuate such ignorance!

And, on Columbus' behalf, we can easily say he was twice the navigator Amerigo Vespucci was¹³, and certainly much less the forgerer, if we can assign blame to Vespucci for the lack of belief in his 1st & 4th voyages (which indeed have the gall to appear in his "*Letter to Soderini*" (1505), a feat which Columbus never deigned to do, as assigned to his reputation, since there is little doubt that Columbus himself sailed on his 1st & 4th voyages! Note how coy the forgerer was to assign four voyages to Vespucci, not unlike Vespucci's rival Columbus, and to take the crown of having America named in Vespucci's honor- the height of injustice to Columbus, who did not dilly-dally with the truth as he understood it, nor have false flatterers win the ultimate prize: the naming of the continent in the wrong person's honor!

So, when it comes to the Columbus-Vespucci controversy, if I may name as such, it helps to 'read between the lines' and see that the Columbus supporters were more than just 'sore losers' but rightly verified in their viewpoint. And what is that view point, you say? That the continents of the Americas should be named in Columbus' honor, not his rival Amerigo Vespucci.

And then there was the Poet named Giullano Dati, whose poem celebrating Columbus' discovery of the New World, we have reason to believe, was sung in the streets of Italy in 1493, whose citizens readily embraced Columbus as their own. Already, even then, it becomes apparent, that people of the Old World had already begun celebrating those ideas of which the yet-to-be famous Vespucci had not even begun to espouse: that there was indeed a New World in the vast ocean to the west, not just some new islands of the West Indies. Already, we might say, 'the wisdom of the sailors', those who perhaps understood the implications of Columbus' discovery better than he, was becoming apparent, in this irrepressible celebration of the Italian masses. It was as if a secret has been passed through the streets and thereafter shouted from the rooftops. In modern terms, it was one of those Eureka moments in which the *hoi polloi* unequivocally declared, 'we found it!'

For who would suppose that a pair of continents be named after Vespucci because of the fanaticism of a small sect of Alsatian friars¹⁴, who passed on their zeal to a certain German mapmaker (Waldseemüller) who, according to him, meant the name America only for a small part of Brazil, and then had this name America erroneously understood by other mapmakers to mean one or more continents, and to have this 'error' flourish *ad infinitum*?

In any case, one may say, the name of such continents, whether it contains a suffix of 'America' or 'Columbia,' would still be named after an Italian! In either case, let us not rail any further, but put this controversy to rest.

¹² Britannica.org "The First Voyage of Christopher Columbus"

¹³ Amerigo Vespucci (1454-1512), Italian Explorer and navigator for whom America is named.

¹⁴ This was the association of Humanist scholars formed at Saint-Dié, whose initial intention was to publish a new edition of Ptolemy's *Geography*. But, having become fans of Vespucci and aware of Waldseemüller's skill as a mapmaker, they must have put two and two together and converted the eminent mapmaker to their cause. The rest is history.